

The Role of School Principals in Activating the Community Partnership, in Light of Total Quality Standards

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 06 , 2024</p> <p>Accepted: November 07 , 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Role of School Principals, Activating, Community Partnership</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14041550</p>	<p><i>The school principals should take numerous and tangible leadership roles, which include the activation of community partnership, since they are the one capable of attracting the local community members to actively participate in all school activities, and they are also capable of bringing the society in its political, economical, social, health, and cultural aspects closer to the educational process, therefore this partnership help to support the school activities, shows its effective role in serving the local community members, and increase the level of interest in the educational process from the external society with all its classes and concerns.</i></p> <p><i>The aim of this study is to identify the role of school principals in Irbid city educational directorate in activating the community partnership, in the light o total quality standards. The sample of the study consisted of (422) male and female teachers selected using random sampling in the academic year 2019/2020. . The result shows that in all three dimension," the practices of parent nurturing and education in the home environment, the volunteer programs and the partnership with local community institutions, the communication processes and participation in the decision making: came at the moderate level. The result shows that there is no significant differences in all three dimension at the level ($\alpha=0.05$)</i></p>

Introduction

One of the difficulties and problems that experienced by the educational systems in this century, which may directly affect their outcomes in general, represented in the population growth and result in an increase in the social demand on education, in addition to the absence of total quality elements. Therefore, the attitudes, directions, and opinions of educational thinkers have emerged, which call for the need to restructure the education in a way that ensures the quality of its outputs, and in response to the growth of scientific and technological revolution at the modern world, and the civilized competition that came with it and stressed on the superiority as an urgent requirement, and it also highlight the necessity to develop education and prepare its institutions, as a key standard to judge and evaluate the quality of education and upgrade its institutions. Most developed and developing countries have moved toward building a partnership with community institutions, in an effort to continuously develop the performance of schools, since the countries that seek to revise and develop the education, and reduce the assorted and renewed problems it face always look forward to build a partnership with the civil society with all its categories, sects, and institutions in order to obtain their assistance and support, where without the patronage and support of all the parties it won't be possible to bring about the targeted reform of education.

The experiences of developed countries have confirmed that education advancement can't be achieved without full participation of everyone, since education is a joint process between the state and society and therefore it shouldn't be funded entirely by the government agencies, but all qualified and capable members of society must contribute to the development process, in one way or another (Khalil, 2006). Whenever schools and community organizations work to support the educational process, it will benefit both of the school and the community. The community partnership works to strengthen, support, and improve the quality of programs that benefit the school and the society by using the resources to align with the common, programs, curricula, and objectives (Harvard Family Research Project, 2010).

Al-Hur (2001) and Al-Sunbol (2004) point out that partnership, its principles, and its basics represent an important point in the development and employment of education environmentally and socially, and to create a real partnership between the public and private sectors in order to rebound and promote the education, the idea of education should move from only a government responsibility to as a national issue that needs the support and assistant of all society sectors to promote the concept of citizenship, deepen the spirit of belonging, and the love of homeland based on the cognitive and balanced awareness between the rights and duties. Moreover, the media institutions should contribute to the importance of community participation in the development of

educational process, and emphasize that charitable and voluntary work isn't limited to helping the needy, but it goes beyond that to the participation in development.

In this context, the school principals should take numerous and tangible leadership roles, which include the activation of community partnership, since they are the one capable of attracting the local community members to actively participate in all school activities, and they are also capable of bringing the society in its political, economical, social, health, and cultural aspects closer to the educational process, therefore this partnership help to support the school activities, shows its effective role in serving the local community members, and increase the level of interest in the educational process from the external society with all its classes and concerns.

School principal plays a key role to encourage the local community, and to attract its members and institutions to support and contribute to the various school programs by highlighting the things that school can provide to the surrounding community and by offering the services in the following two dimensions:

First dimension: the role of school administration in community service:

The society service in modern era considers one of the most important services that provided by school, like adult education, and volunteer work to serve the community, such as trees planting, cleaning campaigns, conducting awareness lectures, etc. which leads to the fulfillment of society responsibilities toward itself and the school that contributes to its prosperity and well-being (Estateah, 2004).

Second dimension: the relationship of school with the local community:

Education is a social process and a social system, where the school is a social institution that has been established to serve the society and raise its children, since the success of school depends on its organic association with the society in which it is located, therefore it became the duty of school administration to document its relationship with the surrounding environment (Al-Hur, 2001).

Study Problems & Questions

Based on the displayed information, and in view of the importance of quality and its criteria as one of the community partnership standards and controls that it hope to be achieved, which have been confirmed by many of the previous studies such as the study of (Al-Showeih, 2010), (Al-Shariy, 2007) study, (Al-Hamdan & Al-Ansari, 2007) study, and the study of (Al-Saaddat, 2002).

The researcher noticed deficiencies in the aspects of community partnership and also noticed doubts about the nature of efforts and actions that school principals perform in the field of activating parent councils and attracting local community members to participate in supporting the school activities. From here, the study problem was formulated in its pursuit to identify the role of school principals at the Directorate of Qasabat Irbid in activating community partnership, in light of total quality standards. Therefore, the study problem can be formulated by answering the following questions:

What is the practice degree of principals at the Directorate of Qasabat Irbid in activating community partnership, in light of the total quality standards from the standpoint of teachers?

Are there any statistically significant differences at level ($\alpha=0.05$) in the responses of study sample members about the practice degree of schools principals in activating the community partnership, in light of the total quality standards, due to the variables of (educational stage, years of service, training courses)?

Study Objectives

The study aims to identify the role of principals at the Directorate of Qasabat Irbid in activating the community partnership, in light of the total quality standards and the different degree of its practice according to the variables (educational stage, years of service, and training courses).

Study Importance

The importance of the study can be highlighted through the following points:

It's expected that decision makers in the Ministry of Education benefit from the results of this study to urge and persuade the school principals to activate the community partnership.

There is hope that school principals at all educational levels will benefit in activating and improving the community partnership process, and increasing the communication and relations with all the local institutions.

It's expected that study results will benefit the people responsible for the school principals' training programs by conducting the training programs related to the activation of community partnership.

Study Methodology

Researcher used the descriptive approach in this study, as a survey to identify the practice degree of school principals at the Directorate of Qasabat Irbid to activate the community partnership, in light of the total quality standards from the standpoint of teachers.

Study Population:

The study society is made up of all teachers at the Directorate of Qasabat Irbid for the school year (2019/2020), who amounted to 422 teachers(male &female).

Study Sample:

A simple random sample was selected which represent the study society very well,

Study Tool:

The researcher used the questionnaire as a tool for the current study which consists of 30 items, and included three fields that are distributed according to the following order:

First Field: the practices of parent nurturing and education in the home environment, which include (13) items.

Second Fields: the volunteer programs and the partnership with local community institutions, which include (8) items.

Third Field: the communication processes and participation in the decision making, which include (9) items.

Conventional and Procedural Definitions:

Partnership: Al- Shariy (2007) defines it as giving a real role and opportunities to society members, such as parents, families, parents' councils, and local community institutions in order to improve the quality of education.

Community Partnership: the contribution of private sector, such of institutions, companies, bodies, associations, and individuals to support the scientific research by providing the financial, ethical, and intellectual support (Al-Hamdan & Al-Ansari, 2007), while the researcher defines it as all forms of cooperation between the school and civil institutions in order to improve quality of education, in light of the total quality standards.

Total Quality Standards: Hassan (1994) defined it as the standardize specifications that can be determined numerically and methodically, through a scientifically arbitration lists that were done by the international arbitrators to judge the **performance of institutions**. This study defines it as the internationally recognized standards that use to judge the community partnership quality.

Study Limitations & Constraints:

Objective (Academic) Limitation: the study was limited in its objective limit to the teachers of public schools.

Spatial limit: the study was limited to Irbid education schools.

Human Constraints: the study was limited to a sample of Irbid education schools teachers.

Temporal limit: the school year (2019/2020).

Previous Studies

A study conducted by Jung and Sheldon (2020) to examine how principals and family partnership is related to family engagement in their children education. Data was collected from (380) schools nationwide. Results showed that more active engagement of families by teachers was associated with strong transformational leadership for partnerships. Also, principal's strong collaborative leadership for partnerships was related to the quality of partnership program organization, which was then associated with the percent of teachers practicing active engagement of families.

Al- Muttawteh study (2019) aimed to identify the role of school principals in Kuwait state about activating the community partnership by providing the necessary requirements to support people with special needs, where the study sample consisted of (277) male and female school teachers at the elementary and middle school in Kuwait. Results showed that role of school principals in Kuwait about activating the community partnership by providing the necessary requirements to support people with special needs came medium, while the field of activating partnership with the members of local community came first, followed by the field of activating partnership with the bodies, association, and institutions of local community. Results also showed nonexistence of statistically significant differences in the estimates of study sample members, according to the variables of gender, experience, and the educational qualification. In light of the results, the researcher made several recommendations which include the need to encourage school principals in Kuwait to activate the community partnership to support people with special needs.

A study conducted by FitzGerald & Quiñones,(2019) aimed to identify the role of school principal in activating the real partnership with students' parents and with the local community organizations, where the study sample consisted of a case study for a school in Pennsylvania. Study results concluded that students' results have improved as a result of democratic dialogue, building confidence, fruitful differences, and the promotion of dialogue. Based on these results, study recommended that educational administrations should activate the partnership with society, due to its positive role on education outcomes by motivating the society institutions to provide grants to the educational institutions.

A study by Pavlakis (2018) to build partnerships with homeless and highly mobile families, population of this study was and drawing from 132 interviews with parents, school personnel, and community stakeholders in an urban district, the result shows that (a) interviewees had divergent experiences with family, school, and community partnerships; (b) some school actors were better positioned to engage HHM families than others; and (c) the diverse residential context of families molded partnership building in unique ways.

The study of Hartman, Stotts, Ottley& Miller(2017) to describe meaningful partnership which contribute a increased school success in rural setting in the U.S.A. Its found that facilitating positive outcomes for young children. Specifically, when community entities and local school professionals work together, there is a greater likelihood of positive outcomes for children.

A research by Islahuddin; and Ismail (2016) aims to describe functions of education played by the family, school, community, and government in education partnerships in Makassar/ Indonesia. A qualitative approach case study were used. Interviews, observation, and documentation were used for data collection. Its found that

the role of the family in the function of education is not run optimally, the role of the school in the function of education shows a great achievement,, the role of the community in the function of education is very diverse and , the role of government in the function of education is conceptually comprehensive.

The study of Ali (2012) aimed to specify and identify the functional requirements for building the required community partnership in the school planning to reach the criteria for building the community partnership in the school funding, as well as the special conditions of community partnership in making decisions, where the study sample consisted of (114) teachers in the vocational schools. The study results found that (86%) from the study sample responded that there are no advisory committees from the local industry businessmen involved in the school planning, while (69%) replied that there is no participation from the managers with the factories' owners to determine the society requirements needed by the labor market. Results also indicated that (80%) replied that school don't participate with the private or national association in projects that have financial return, and that school don't allow the dialogue between the different sections inside the school.

The study of Raal,(2010) addressed the dimensions of quality standards from the quantitative and qualitative aspects, which should be included in making the partnership and integration a reality between the educational institutions and surrounding environments in the United States of America, where the study sample consisted of (785) managers. One of the most important results of the study was that community partnership elements by the local community institutions must be based on global quality standards, in order for it to contribute to a productive community partnership. Study also concluded that quality factors must be subject to the evaluation and measurement periodically and regularly, in order to develop the community partnership processes, especially in the era of educational openness on the society institutions.

In the study of Al-Hamdan and Al-Ansari (2007), the researchers aimed to identify the reality and types of community partnership in the financing of educational projects at the secondary schools in Kuwait, and also aimed to propose facilities and standards related to the finance of educational projects, where the study sample included (120) male and female of the secondary schools principals. Study results showed that the largest funding for educational projects falls in the honor of outstanding students, where it came in the first place with (51.4%), the second place of (46%) was for providing schools with computers, the third place of (42.1%) was for the cash contributions, and the last place of (5.6%) was in favor of building the educational laboratories.

Finally, the study of (Mernda, 2000) aimed to identify the education participation during the years (1990-2000) in United States of America and to identify the current status of community institutions participation in education, where the study sample amounted to (556) educational areas. The study results found that community partnership in education had expanded clearly and effectively towards the implementation of community partnership in education in 2000 compared with 1990.

Study Results & Discussion

The first question that states: What is the practice degree of principals at the Directorate of Qasabat Irbid in activating the community partnership, in light of the total quality standards from the standpoint of teachers?

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for all fields of school principals' practices to their roles in the community partnership at the three fields of study. The study results on the first question came as shown in table (1) below:

Table (1) arithmetic means and standard deviations for all fields of school principals' practices at the Directorate of Qasabat Irbid for their roles in the community partnership in the light of the total quality standards, from the standpoint of teachers

No	Field	Mean	STDEV	Rank	Practice Degree
First	Parenting and education practices in the home environment	3.02	0.54	2	Medium
Second	Volunteer educational programs and partnership with the local community institutions	3.13	0.57	1	Medium
Third	Communication and participation processes in the decision making	2.99	0.60	3	Medium
	Overall Practice Degree	3.04	0.45	-	Medium

In regard to the results of first field, which states "the parenting and education practices in the home environment", the arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated and the results shown in table (2) below :

Table (2) arithmetic means and standard deviations for the items of first field

No	Items	Rank	Mean	STDEV	Degree
1	Offer information about the educational services provided to students and their parents at the school	1	3.33	1.18	Medium
2	Holds specialized regular meetings for students' parents	2	3.19	1.04	Medium

	about their children growth				
4	Conduct a ceremony to honor the parents who participate in the school's events	3	3.13	1.08	Medium
7	Inform parents about the rules of attendance	4	3.07	1.15	Medium
8	Inform parents about the behavior that must be followed inside the school	5	3.06	1.24	Medium
5	Let parents participate in the presentation of educational activities and services to students	6	3.04	1.11	Medium
13	Propose study schedules for students to do their homework at home	7	3.02	1.13	Medium
3	Encourage parents to raise their children on respecting the cultural polarity or multi-culture of school students	8	2.96	1.077	Medium
6	Invite parents to participate in supporting educational programs and services provided by the school	9	2.90	1.13	Medium
9	Respects the different cultures and races that students belong to inside the school	10	2.87	1.12	Medium
12	Guides students' families to help their children select the appropriate study programs for them	11	2.85	1.14	Medium
10	Oversee the introduction of specialized vocational educational consultations for parents	12	2.83	1.19	Medium
11	Follow up on the methods that parents use to deal with their children' problems	13	2.79	1.12	Medium
	General Average		3.01	0.53	Medium

It shows from table (2) that overall arithmetic mean of study sample responses on the items of first field that measure the practice degree of school principals to activate the community partnership in the field of parental education and learning practices at the home environment, in light of the total quality standards from the standpoint of teachers equal to (3.01) with a medium degree and standard deviation of (0.53). In addition, all items came at a medium degree with an arithmetic mean between (2.79) and (3.33), as shown in table (2) above. The researcher attributes that to the lack of permanent and clear methods of communication between the school and the parents of students, the lack of cultural awareness of parents about the importance of school role, and the lack of some school principals to social communication skills with parents since it doesn't form part of the training programs of school principals, as well as the preoccupation of parents with many things that keep them away from communicating with the school.

These results disagree with the results of many previous studies, such as Al-Hamdan and Al-Ansari (2007) which aimed to identify the reality and types of community participation in the financing of educational projects, while it agree with the study of (FitzGerald & Quiñones, 2019) which aimed to identify the role of school principal in activating the real partnership with the parents of students and with the local community organizations.

In regard to the results of second field, which states "Volunteer educational programs and partnership with the local community institutions", the arithmetic means and standard deviations were computed for each item of the field, which measures practice degree of school principals in activating the community partnership in the voluntary educational programs and in partnership with local community institutions, in light of the total quality standards from the standpoint of teachers, as shown in table (3) below:

Table (3) arithmetic means and standard deviations for the items of second field

No	Items	Rank	Mean	STDE V	Degree
14	Prepare a study at the beginning of school year to reveal the willingness of parents to participate in the volunteer works	1	3.63	1.20	Large
15	Organize plans for the volunteer works in school with the participation of parents	2	3.51	1.17	Large
16	Make an announcement about voluntary educational programs to attract the local community members to participate in it	3	3.06	1.01	Medium
17	Put the various school facilities at the service of local community	4	3.04	1.05	Medium
20	Offers an educational archaeological programs	5	2.95	1.08	Medium

	after the school day				
21	Cooperate with the local community organizations to deliver programs that support the students' skills	6	3.91	1.16	Medium
18	Reward parents of students who are outstanding and distinguished in the school service	7	3.91	1.16	Medium
19	Provide guidebook about school programs that local community institutions can participate in	8	2.86	1.09	Medium
	General Average		3.11	0.56	Medium

It shows from table (3) that overall arithmetic mean or general average of study sample responses on the items of second field that measure the practice degree of school principals to activate the community partnership in the field of volunteer educational programs and partnership with the local community institutions, in light of total quality standards from the standpoint of teachers equal to (3.11) with a medium degree and standard deviation of (0.56). In addition, the average responses of study sample members on the (8) items were two items at large degree and (6) items at medium degree as showed in table (3) above.

The researcher attributes this result to the lack of institutions that are interested in providing the specialized training to students after school and the non-existence of voluntary training centers that provide free courses to raise the students' efficiency in the various fields, due to the lack of financial means and the lack of financial support provided by parents for the school programs, as well as the disparity of authority degree granted to school principals in attracting the institutions to support and establish the projects inside the schools, and if it these projects were found it will be controlled by complex laws from the relevant authorities. In addition, the poor attention of school principals to communicate with the local community institutions to obtain support for conducting after-school training courses, due to lack of principals' desire to work after school.

In regard to the results of third field, which states "Communication and participation processes in the decision making" the arithmetic means and standard deviations were calculated for each item of the field, which measures the practice degree of school principals in activating the community partnership in the communication and participation processes in decision making, in light of the total quality standards from the standpoint of teachers, as shown in table (4) below:

Table (4) arithmetic means and standard deviations for the items of third field

Number	Items	Rank	Mean	STDEV	Degree
22	Publish electronic regular reports that include the school activities	1	3.33	1.31	Medium
23	Supports effective two-way communication channels between the school and parents of students	2	3.31	1.19	Medium
24	Communicate with parents through periodic reports related to the performance of their children to express their opinions about it	3	2.93	1.03	Medium
30	Keen to parents' support for the decisions of therapeutic programs implementation for students	4	2.93	1.03	Medium
28	Invites parents to attend a meeting about the culture of school quality	5	2.88	1.15	Medium
25	Be different in the use of available methods to invite parents to attend the meetings of parents and teachers Board	6	2.87	1.09	Medium
29	Benefit from the opinions of parents to identify the vision and mission of school	7	2.82	1.10	Medium
27	Let representatives of parents to get membership in the school's advisory boards and its special committees.	8	2.82	1.18	Medium
26	Encourage teachers to continuously communicate with parents to show them the way to do required homework	9	2.07	1.16	Medium
	General Average		2.97	0.59	Medium

It shows from table (4) that overall arithmetic mean or general average of study sample responses on the items of second field that measure the practice degree of school principals to activate the community partnership in the field of communication and participation processes in the decision making, in light of total quality standards from the standpoint of teachers equal to (2.97) with a medium degree and a standard deviation of (0.59). In addition, all items came at a medium degree with an arithmetic mean between (2.07) and (3.33), as shown in table (4) above.

The researcher attributes these results to the fact that public administrations kept on identifying different school activities, at the beginning of school year and only specifying two weekly lessons to conduct the different school activities while being careless in obligating schools to provide the required periodic reports about the various school activities of the Directorate of Education, and the negligence in utilizing these classes for the various school activities. In addition, the negligence of activating various communication methods in order to send the periodic written reports about the methodological and non-methodological achievements of students, which are needed by parents to communicate with the school principals and teachers, activate the community partnership, and benefit from the opinions of parents to identify the vision and mission of school. According to the researcher knowledge, there is no active system that obliges school principals to develop the vision and mission of school, and also to require it to activate the advisory councils inside and outside the school, which led to the poor representation of parents in the membership of these advisory councils and committees.

The second question that states: Are there any statistically significant differences at level ($\alpha=0.05$) in the arithmetic means of study sample members' responses about the practice degree of schools principals at the Directorate of Qasabat Irbid in activating the community partnership, in light of the total quality standards, due to the variables of (educational stage, years of service)?

To answer this question about the educational stage variable, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the community partnership fields which are practiced by the school principals were calculated according to the educational stage variable. The results indicated the existence of an apparent differences between the arithmetic means according to the educational stage, where the overall degree of the three fields as a whole that are represented by the (F) value amounted to (0.19), which isn't statistically significant at the level ($\alpha<0.05$) and indicates the nonexistence of statistical differences between the arithmetic means study sample members' responses, according to the educational stage variable.

The researcher attributes the previous results to the similar opinions of teachers at the different educational stages of primary and secondary, with regard to practice degree of school principals in activating the community partnership at the three fields which obtained a medium practice degree; as indicated by the descriptive statistical results. Therefore, the researcher sees the importance of urging and directing the school principals to activate the community partnership in all school stages; in light of the total quality standards.

To answer this question about the years of service variable, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the community partnership fields which are practiced by the school principals were calculated according to the years of service variable. The results indicated the existence of an apparent differences between the arithmetic means according to the years of service variable, and indicated a statistically significant differences at all fields of the tool; as a whole in the light of the total quality standards at the significant level of ($\alpha=0.05$). Results also indicate a statistically significant differences between the arithmetic means of study sample members' responses, due to years of service variable where the Scheffe' test indicated that the differences between arithmetic mean of (3.10) is in favor of less than (5) years of experience, while the arithmetic mean for the years of experience which are more than (10) years was (2.98).

The researcher attributes these results to the high values of arithmetic means for the study sample members with few years of experience (less than 5 yrs) compared to the arithmetic means' values of the study sample members' responses with the large years of experience (over 10 years), with the fact that sample study with the experience of less than (5) years may have satisfaction and confidence in the school principals' practices for the three fields of study; as the higher compared with the number of study sample of more than (10) years) of experience, which may be attributed to their long experience, and knowledge and concepts provided for them in this field. Therefore, this makes them believe that the practice degree of school principals in this field should be better than that, and as a result arithmetic means of their responses came less than the less experienced members.

Recommendations

- 1- The necessity of working to activate parenting practices and learning in the home environment to a high societal partnership to solve the problems of his children and provide professional educational consultations by school principals
- 2-The importance of working to activate the field of voluntary educational programs and partnership with local community institutions by providing guidelines for school programs that they can participate in providing programs which support students' skills.
- 3- The necessity of working to activate the field of communication operations and participation in decision-making to reach a high societal participation by encouraging teachers to communicate with parents of students.

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